

Breeding methods

Development of dihaploid rice lines through anther culture (I)

A. E. Draz, Rice Research and Training Centre, Sakha, Kafri- El-Sheikh, Egypt; F. J. Zapata and G. S. Khush, IRRI

We developed homozygous rice lines through anther culture, using crosses of blast (Bl)-resistant (indica/japonica) Korean varieties with Bl-susceptible Egyptian varieties.

Anthers from five F_1 crosses were inoculated on callus induction media G1, Fj, and L8, used routinely in the IRRI Tissue Culture Laboratory. The media varied in their basal composition and in 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA), and kinetin (Kin) concentrations. Calli were plated in eight regeneration media differing in Kin, NAA, and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) concentrations.

Callus induction efficiency in all three media was relatively high, indicating that all could be used for these crosses (Table 1). Callus induction percentage varied with genotype; those with a japonica female parent were more responsive. For example, Giza 171/C731135 had the highest callus production percentage on G1 and L8.

Green plant regeneration ranged from 0.4% to 7.7% (Table 2). Genotypes

Table 1. Calli induced from F_1 crosses in different callus induction media. ^a IRRI, 1990 dry season (DS).

Cross combination (F_1)	G1		Fj		L8		Av calli produced ^b (%)
	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	
Nahda/Milyang 85	660	27.3	660	39.3	1080	50.5	41.1
Giza 14/Milyang 85	2040	41.4	1320	37.1	1320	37.8	39.2
GZ1343-8/C731135	840	33.3	1020	30.8	900	43.3	35.6
Giza 171/C731135	1440	60.4	2220	30.3	1500	51.3	44.8
GZ3030-11-1-3/Suweon 346	600	19.1	720	18.7	720	11.1	16.1
Total	5580		5940		5520		
Average ^a (%)		41.4		40.6		41.4	

^a Concentrations of 2,4-D, NAA, and Kin (mg/liter) = G1 = 2.0, 2.5, 0.75, Fj = 0.5, 2.5, 0.5, L8 = 0.5, 3.5, 2.0.

^b $\frac{\text{Anthers producing callus}}{\text{Total anthers plated}} \times 100$

Table 2. Green plant regeneration from 5 F_1 crosses in 8 media. IRRI, 1990 DS.

Cross combination (F_1)	Regeneration frequency (%)									Calli producing green plants	
	MI	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	SK-11	no.	% ^a	
Nahdamilyang 85	4.2	5.9	6.0	1.7	5.6	8.4	9.5	8.7	61	6.2	
Giza 14/Milyang 85	3.6	4.3	6.5	5.1	4.6	7.6	3.1	4.7	87	4.7	
GZ1343-8/C731135	0	1.2	2.5	0.6	0.7	0	0	2.8	9	0.8	
Giza 171/C731135	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.6	10	0.4	
GZ3030- 11-1-3/Suweon 346	8.9	2.9	2.2	6.7	2.0	1.5	1.8	5.7	23	7.7	
Calli producing green plants (no.)	18	24	27	20	20	25	27	29	190		
Average ^a (%)	2.7	2.8	3.0	2.4	3.1	4.1	3.3	3.6	-	3.1	

^a $\frac{\text{Calli (no.) producing green plants}}{\text{Calli (total no.) transferred}} \times 100$

differed in their response to different plant regeneration media. Media M6, M7, and SK-11 gave the highest green plant percentages. Kin concentrations of M6, M7, and SK-11 were 8, 16, and 1 mg/liter, respectively. BAP (1 mg/liter) and casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter)

were added to the SK-11 medium.

This study produced 794 homozygous diploid plants from 190 calli derived from the anther culture of five F_1 crosses. These anther culture-derived lines will be tested against available Bl races under Egyptian conditions. □

Development of dihaploid rice lines through anther culture (II)

A. E. Draz, Rice Research and Training Centre, Sakha, Kafri- El-Sheikh, Egypt; F. J. Zapata and G. S. Khush, IRRI

Saline areas worldwide are increasing for several reasons, including high water tables. Such areas need high-yielding rice varieties with satisfactory levels of salinity tolerance as well as other characteristics, such as short stature, high tillering ability, blast resistance, and

Table 1. Percentage callus induction of F_1 crosses in different callus induction media. IRRI, 1990 dry season (DS).

Cross combination (F_1)	G1		Fj		L8		Av calli produced ^a (%)
	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (%)	
Giza 159/C732048	1800	34.7	2040	26.8	1380	37.3	32.3
Agami M-1/C731135	1080	25.9	960	21.8	1620	33.6	28.3
GZ1368-5-4/Niigatawase	1860	11.8	2880	14.4	3120	20.8	12.9
GZ1368-5-4/C731135	1260	13.5	2520	11.1	2040	16.9	13.7
GZ2447S-17/C732048	960	12.2	1320	14.2	1560	17.6	15.1
Total	6960		9720		9720		
Average ^a (%)		19.9		16.9		23.5	

^a $\frac{\text{Anthers producing callus}}{\text{Total anthers plated}} \times 100$

acceptable grain shape and quality. Anther culture through doubled-haploid breeding could help achieve these objectives.

In Egypt, saline areas represent more than 30% of the total rice-growing area. Five crosses for these areas were selected to study callus and plant regeneration efficiencies and to get homozygous lines tolerant of salinity. The cross combinations were japonica//indica/japonica (crosses 1 and 2); indica/japonica//japonica (cross 3); and indica/japonica//indica/japonica (crosses 4 and 5).

Anthers were plated in media routinely used in the IRRI tissue culture laboratory, three for callus induction and eight for plant regeneration.

On average, the L8 medium induced the highest rate of calli (Table 1). Highest callus induction rates were in Giza 159/C732048 (32.3%) and Agami M-1/C731135 (28.3%). These crosses have japonica female parents. Efficiency-

Table 2. Percentage and number of green plants produced in 8 plant regeneration media for 5 F₁ crosses. IRRI, 1990 DS.

Cross	Green plant regeneration frequency (%)								Calli producing green plants	
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	SK-11	no.	% ^a
Giza 159/C732048	0.4	1.7	5.4	2.3	1.3	0.6	1.4	2.1	32	2.0
Agami M-1/C731135	0.9	0.6	1.0	0.7	0.7	1.4	1.2	2.9	10	1.0
GZ1368-5-4/Niigatawase	0.7	1.7	4.2	6.3	2.0	2.0	0	0	19	1.5
GZ1368-5-4/C731135	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.0	0	1	2.0
GZ2447S-17/C732048	0	0	0	6.3	4.0	2.2	1.2	0	8	2.0
Calli producing green plants (no.)	3	9	18	16	5	6	6	7	70	
Average ^a (%)	0.8	1.2	2.3	2.4	1.2	1.3	0.9	1.3		1.6

^a Total calli producing green plants / Total calli plated for regeneration × 100

cies were lower in crosses with indica/japonica parents (GZ1368-5-4 and GZ2447S-17).

For plant regeneration, eight media differing in kinetin (Kin), indole-acetic acid (IAA), and naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA) concentrations were used. Green plant regeneration efficiency was

generally low (Table 2). The M3 and M4 media gave the highest regeneration percentages. M3 has 5 mg Kin and 1 mg IAA/liter; M4 has 2 mg Kin and 1 mg NAA/liter. Plant regeneration capacity of the media varied according to genotype. A total of 325 plants were regenerated from 70 calli. □

Interaction of media for callus induction and for plant regeneration in rice anther culture

A. E. Draz, Rice Research and Training Centre, Sakha, Kafr El-Sheikh, Egypt; F. J. Zapata and G. S. Khush, IRRI

The response of a genotype grown in vitro depends to a large extent on the composition of the culture medium. Usually, callus induction is in a medium different from that for plant regeneration. This makes it important to identify the best combination of media for tissue culture.

We plated anthers of five F₁ rice crosses bred for Egyptian conditions on three callus induction media and eight plant regeneration media. The callus induction media G1, Fj, and L8 differed in their basal composition as well as in hormone concentrations. The basal medium of Fj is B5, that of L8 is N6, that of G1 is a combination of B5 and MS. Respectively, G1, Fj, and L8, have 0.75, 0.5, and 2 mg kinetin (Kin)/liter; 2.0, 0.5 mg of 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)/liter; and 2.5, 2.5, and 3.5

Table 1. Callus induction efficiency of 5 F₁ crosses in 3 callus induction media.

Cross	Callus induction ^a (%)			Average ^b (%)
	G1	Fj	L8	
Nahda/Milyang 85	13.48	38.79	50.79	34.55
Giza 14/Milyang 85	36.50	38.97	58.60	44.38
Giza 159/C732048	38.50	29.10	37.80	35.55
Giza 171/C731135	45.60	35.10	37.50	40.00
GZ2175-5-3/C731135	27.80	41.30	25.64	30.61
Average (%) ^b	32.40	36.67	42.06	
LSD (crosses) 0.05 = ns. 0.01 = ns				
LSD (media) 0.05 = 1.67. 0.01 = 2.20				

^a Six hundred anthers per cross were plated on each medium.

^b Total anthers with calli / Total anthers plated × 100

mg of naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA)/liter.

The basal medium for plant regeneration was Murashige and Skoog's. Kinetin concentrations (mg/liter) differ for M1, M2, M3, M4, M5, M6, M7, and SK-11: 1, 10, 5, 2, 4, 8, 16, and 1, respectively. All the media have 1 mg NAA/l except M3, which has 1 mg indole 3-acetic acid (IAA)/l instead of NAA. SK-11 also includes benzylamino purine (1mg/liter) and casein hydrolysate (500 mg/liter).

In callus induction, there was a significant interaction between crosses and media, and significant differences among the three media (Table 1).

Table 2. Interaction between callus induction medium and plant regeneration medium in anther culture of 5 cross combinations.

Callus induction medium	Green plants (%) from regeneration medium								Total (no.)	Av (%) ^a
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	SK-11		
G1	1.8	2.3	4.8	1.4	4.3	1.8	5.8	2.4	79	2.9
Fj	0.9	0.7	2.5	3.5	2.0	1.8	3.6	3.6	58	2.2
L8	3.0	4.5	4.9	4.3	4.5	4.1	2.9	5.1	108	4.1
Total no.	16	30	43	31	26	29	35	35	245	
Av (%) ^a	3.0	1.8	2.4	4.1	3.0	3.1	3.9	2.8		3.3

^a Total calli producing green plants / Total calli plated for regeneration × 100